

ISMOIL SOMONIY MAQBARASI**Rasulova Mohichehra Maston qizi**

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“Tarix va filologiya” kafedrası o’qituvchisi.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada Markaziy Osiyodagi eng qadimiy va me’moriy jihatdan eng go’zal inshootlardan biri bo’lgan Ismoil Somoniy maqbarasi tahlil qilingan.

Kalit so’zlar: Somoniylar, maqbara, nekropol, chor, Movarounnahr, Xuroson, Ismoil Somoniy.

ISMAIL SOMONI MAUSOLEUM

Abstract. This article analyzes the Ismail Somoni Mausoleum, one of the oldest and most architecturally beautiful structures in Central Asia.

Keywords: Samanids, mausoleum, necropolis, tsar, Maveronnahr, Khorasan, Ismail Somoni.

МАВЗОЛЕЙ ИСМАИЛА СОМОНИ

Аннотация. В статье анализируется мавзолей Исмаила Сомони, одно из древнейших и красивейших в архитектурном отношении сооружений в Средней Азии.

Ключевые слова: Саманиды, мавзолей, некрополь, царь, Моваруннахр, Хорасан, Исмаил Саманид.

Yurtimiz tarixiga nazar tashlarkanmiz o’zining ko’p asrlik boy madaniyati bilan hanuzgacha kishini lol qoldirib kelmoqda. Chunonchi, moddiy madaniyat namunalaridan biri bo’lgan me’morchilik durdonalarini bunga misol tariqasida keltirsak bo’ladi. Jumladan, O’rta Osiyo arxitekturasi va me’morchiligida o’ziga xos o’ringa ega bo’lgan tarixiy yodgorliklarimizdan biri bo’lgan Ismoil Somoniy maqbarasini fikrimizni dalili desak mubolag’a qilmagan bo’lamiz. Bu tarixiy obida nafaqat Buxoro, balki O’rta Osiyo me’morchiligi va san’ati tarixida dastlabki maqbaralardan biri bo’lgan. Maqbaraning bunyod etilishi Somoniylar davlati hukmdori, yirik siyosiy arbob Ismoil Somoniy nomi bilan bog’liq.

Ismoil Somoniy shaxsi haqida gapiradigan bo’lsak, u 848-yil Buxoro shahrida tug’ilgan, 874-yilda somoniylarning Buxorodagi noibi, 888-yildan esa butun Movarounnahr o’z hukmronligini o’rnatadi. 900-yilda esa Movarounnahr va Xurosonni birlashtirgan. Buxoro shahrini mamlakat poytaxti deb e’lon qiladi. Ismoil Somoniy markaziy hokimiyatni mustahkamlash maqsadida, turli hududlardan ulamolalar, adiblar, usta va hunarmandlarni

Buxoroga to‘plagan¹. Mamlakatda obodonlashtirish, shaharsozlikni yuksaltirib, madaniyat rivojiga katta hissa qo‘shadi. Bag‘dod xalifalaridan ibrat olib, o‘ziga ulkan maqbara qurdiradi.

Ismoil Somoniy maqbarasi o‘rta asrlarning rivojlangan davrida (IX-X asr), taxminan 892-907-yillarda, hozirgi Buxoroning eski shahar qismida qurilgan².

Ismoil Somoniy maqbarasi IX asrda Buxoroda me‘morchilik san‘ati, binokorlik texnikasining naqadar yuksalganligini va rivojlanganligini ko‘rsatadi. Bu me‘moriy obidaning qurilishida qadimiy so‘g‘d me‘morchiligi an‘analaridan ham foydalanilganligi ushbu nodir obidani tiklashgacha bo‘lgan davrda Buxoroda me‘morchilik, arxitektura rivojlangini bildiradi. Somoniylar maqbarasi loyihasidan tortib, hajmiy tuzilishigacha geometrik tartib va qoida asosida yaratilganligi yuksak professional darajaga ega bo‘lgan tajribali quruvchilar va malakali me‘morlarning loyihalash va qurilish texnikasiga oid bilim va malakalarga nechog‘lik boy bo‘lishganini ko‘rsatadi.

Maqbara Movarounnahr va Xuroson me‘morchiligining o‘ziga xos 4 tomoni bir xil “chor“ uslubida qurilgan. Maqbaraning dizayni esa jimjima g‘ishtin bezaklari chiviqli to‘siq yoki qamish, bo‘yra to‘qimasini eslatadi. Binoning yuqori qismi gumbaz bilan qoplangan bo‘lib, bu islom me‘morchiligida keng tarqalgan uslubdir. To‘rt burchagi ustunsimon shaklda ishlangan, gumbaz atrofiga 4 qubba o‘rnatilgan. Devor tepasida kungirasimon 40 ta darcha bilan bilan ziynatlangan. Qurilishda o‘ymakorlik naqshlaridan ham foydalanilgan bo‘lib, har bir g‘isht o‘ziga xos geometrik shakllar va bezaklar bilan ishlangan³.

Ismoil Somoniy arxitekturaviy yodgorligi XI asrdan ortiq vaqt ichida tabiiy ofatlar va inson omillariga qaramay yaxshi holda saqlanib qolgan. Yodgorlik nafaqat Buxoroda, balki Markaziy Osiyo o‘rta asr me‘morchiligida ham yangi uslublarning shakllanishiga ta‘sir ko‘rsatgan va keyinchalik boshqa ko‘plab maqbara va masjidning qurilishida ilhom manbai bo‘lgan desak adashmagan bo‘lamiz.

Maqbara birinchi marta 1924-yilda Moisei Ginzburg ekspeditsiya guruhi tomonidan tekshirilgan. 1925-yilda Buxoro tarixiy va san‘at yodgorliklarini muhofaza qilish komissiyasining ilmiy kotibi Muso Saidjonov bino gumbazining astarlarini tiklashni tashkil qilgan. Vasiliy Vyatkin boshchiligida arxeologik tadqiqotlarda 1926—1928-yillarda olib borilgan qazishmalar davomida nekropol ichida bir nechta qabrlar, jumladan Ismoil Somoniyning o‘ligi saqlanib qolganligi aniqlangan⁴.

¹ <https://meros.uz/object/ismoil-somoniy-maqbarasi>

² Булатов М. С. “Мавзолей Саманидов — жемчужина архитектуры Средней Азии” М. 1978

³ Булатов М. С. “Геометрическая гармонизация в архитектуре Средней Азии IX–XV веков” Т. 1976

⁴ Ремпель Л. И. “Далёкое и близкое: страницы жизни, быта, строительного дела, ремесла и искусства Старой Бухары” Т. 1981

Hozirgi kunda me'moriy inshoot atroflari bog'ga aylantirilgan. U arxiologik qazishmalar orqali topilganligi uchun 60-50 sm pastda joylashgan. Bugungi kunda bu inshoot islom dunyosi ma'rifatparvarlari va allomalarining diqqat-markazida hamda turistlarning sayohatgohiga aylangan.

1993-yilda bu maqbara "Butunjahon madaniy meroslari ro'yxati"ga kiritilgan. 1997-yilda Buxoro shahrining 2500 yilligi munosabati bilan Buxorodagi barcha obidalar qatorida Ismoil Somoniy maqbarasi ham qayta ta'mirdan chiqdi. 2000-yil 30-avgustda "Madaniy meros obyektlarini muhofaza qilish va ulardan foydalanish to'g'risi"dagi qonun qabul qilindi⁵.

Davlatimiz tomonidan qabul qilingan ushbu qonunlar me'moriy inshoot muhofazasining huquqiy kafolatidir.

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⁵ <https://meros.uz/object/ismoil-somoniy-maqbarasi>

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